

Original Research

Small-Scale Agribusiness as Vehicle for Empowerment and Resilience: Lessons from World Vision International, Lesotho

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Abstract

The study sought to understand socio-economic empowerment and resilience through small-scale agribusinesses. Data was collected from 273 beneficiaries of small-scale agro-businesses funded by World Vision International (WVI). Data was collected using a 7-point Likert-based data collection tool. The data was analyzed using SmartPLS 4 and Stata. The analysis suggested that community resilience mediates the relationship between socio-economic empowerment and resilience ($\beta = 0.095$, $p < 0.050$) and that enhancing community resilience results in improved overall resilience ($\beta = 0.796$, $p < 0.001$). It was also determined that socio-economic initiatives based on SSAB significantly increased overall resilience ($\beta = 0.158$, $p < 0.001$). It can be argued that agro-based initiatives can be instrumental in empowering individuals, and this, in turn, results in improved resilience. Further research could be conducted to assess the sustained impact of agricultural interventions and economic empowerment initiatives in Lesotho. One way to do this is through a longitudinal study that evaluates the effectiveness of programs like World Vision International's Livelihoods and Resilience Programme (LRP) on participants' socio-economic outcomes over time.

Keywords: Agribusiness, Resilience, Socio-economic Empowerment.

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Introduction

The absence of sound economic empowerment initiatives in rural communities, including high poverty rates, manifests in several ways. Reducing poverty is an immediate challenge that humanity must address (Hoy & Sumner, 2021). The need to reduce poverty has never been greater. Despite concerted efforts, the population of poor individuals is still increasing (Watkins et al., 2024). Failing to disrupt poverty makes achieving various United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) more difficult. Also, poverty is associated with several adverse outcomes, such as failure to access essential services like healthcare and education, food insecurity, and increased social ills, such as drug abuse and crime (Duong et al., 2021). It also makes individuals less resilient to perturbations, such as environmental disasters, and personal challenges, such as death in the family or illness, that they may face. Given the depth of the adverse outcomes often accompanying poor economic empowerment and high poverty rates, it is unsurprising that several organizations, including World Vision International (WVI), have designed and implemented several initiatives to fight rural poverty through projects that foster economic empowerment. The initiatives by WVI lean towards harnessing the agricultural potential of rural communities. This study, therefore, explores the relationship between economic empowerment through small-scale agribusinesses and resilience.

The government of Lesotho has identified agriculture as one of the crucial sectors due to its role in employing the country's population. However, according to the Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) (2012), the country's agriculture sector is not performing optimally. This conclusion was reached because, among other observations, the country's agricultural value addition accounted for only 15.7 per cent of the GDP even though the agriculture sector employs almost thirty per cent of the country's economically active population. Though the value added by agriculture to GDP is higher than that of other developing countries like South Africa (2.4%) or developed countries like the Netherlands (>10 %), one would expect it to contribute more given the large number of people who are employed in the sector (Directorate: Statistics and Economic Analysis, 2022; Donati & Tukker, 2022). It can, therefore, be argued that there are opportunities to improve the economic impacts of agriculture in Lesotho. This assertion is premised on the observation that Lesotho's dominant forms of agriculture are subsistence and semi-commercial (Mukwada et al., 2020). The need to support the agriculture sector in the country is further heightened by the fact that most farmers in the country have small pieces of land, < 1 ha and such small plots will need to be intensively managed if the farmer is to get meaningful returns from the land (Rantso, 2016).

World Vision International has recognized the value of agro-based projects in economically empowering communities and individuals. Per this vision, WVI has established various income-generating projects in many districts across Lesotho that can be best described as agro-based. These projects include poultry farming and vegetable production. The idea behind establishing these projects is that the communities can use the knowledge gained and resources available to improve agriculture production, which can translate into improvements in their income base. In addition to greater food insecurity, improved on-farm output can help mitigate some of the challenges often

associated with poverty. One of these challenges is poor resilience to life's perturbations (Li et al., 2021).

The environment in which humans exist is increasingly getting unpredictable. The frequency of natural disasters, such as droughts, is increasing. Furthermore, people often struggle with personal disasters that are exacerbated by poverty since most personal challenges usually require financial resources to overcome. This has seen a resurgence in interest concerning the concept of resilience. Promoting resilience at both the micro and macro scale is essential because poor resilience to disturbances can have long-lasting impacts on the welfare of an individual (Tuohy & Stephens, 2012).

Resilience has been defined differently by different scholars. A common definition conceptualizes resilience as the ability to 'bounce' back from a setback or disturbance. The concept entered mainstream developmental literature through the work of Norman Garmezy (1982), who was intrigued by the observation that children who grew up in sub-optimal environments had markedly different life trajectories. Specifically, Garmezy (1993) observed a positive correlation between childhood poverty and struggles later in life. However, some children overcame their past challenges to lead successful lives. Garmezy (1993) described those who led lives of relative success, even though their childhoods were characterized by poverty and related struggles, as being 'resilient'. The concept of resilience has since permeated several other fields, including developmental studies, disaster management, and business management. This study focuses on the role of small-scale agribusinesses as drivers of economic empowerment and how this economic empowerment relates to resilience.

Based on Garmezy's (1993) insight, resilience can be viewed as the ability of an individual, household, or community to maintain acceptable living standards regardless of external factors, such as drought, floods, or personal loss, that may diminish people's capital stocks and relegate them to lower rungs of the socio-economic ladder. Therefore, it is not surprising that sustainable poverty alleviation strategies are often associated with community resilience building. Such initiatives empower individuals in several ways, particularly economically. Economic empowerment initiatives are urgently needed for communities in the developing world that rely on agriculture to sustain livelihoods and do not have limited income-generating opportunities.

In the developing world, small-scale agro-based entrepreneurial ventures have gained favour within the developmental community because they allow individuals to gainfully utilize their most valuable but under-utilized resource, the land. In addition to leveraging the land, several studies have shown that agglomerating farmers into groups or cooperatives makes deploying resources or imparting knowledge easier. In China, for example, the central government is attempting to create a new type of agribusinesses (NTAs) to encourage the development of small-scale agriculture and improve farmer incomes. This approach, characterized by forming farming cooperatives, reduces the costs associated with input procurement and selling farm produce. This approach effectively allows the farmer to have greater profits. Published data indicate that agro-based cooperatives have since been formed in more than 90% of impoverished villages in China, and this initiative has helped approximately 22 million poor people move out of poverty (Qu et al., 2023). In the US, though farmers farm individually, agriculture

cooperatives have the same function of reducing some of the costs associated with farming, particularly input procurement. In Morocco, the government has a program called "MOURAFAKA", created to help create agricultural cooperatives and offer support to the cooperatives. An analysis by Ibourk and El Aynaoui (2023) suggests that the program improves the sustainability of agricultural cooperatives by strengthening their governance, management, and market access capabilities. This approach has been replicated in many areas worldwide, including Lesotho.

World Vision International (WVI) in Lesotho has adopted an approach akin to agricultural cooperatives in China and elsewhere. In this intervention, which aims to reduce poverty and, in doing so, promote resilience to disasters, project beneficiaries are put in groups called small-scale agro-businesses (SSABs). Each SSAB is given resources, such as equipment and capital, to use their land more productively. In addition to capital, the SSAB beneficiaries are also given relevant knowledge to ensure the sustainability and profitability of the ventures. This knowledge includes knowledge on saving and how to interact with markets.

This approach to development hinges on insights gathered from the economic empowerment theory and the human capital approach. The origins of the economic empowerment theory cannot be credited to a single individual as with other theories. Its roots can be traced to the work of classical economists such as Adam Smith, John Stuart Mill, and David Ricardo (Shaikh et al., 2023). These economists argued that economic freedom and entrepreneurship are vital to economic growth. In the context of resilience building, entrepreneurship allows individuals to amass resources to get their lives back to what they were before a disaster. Also linked to the economic empowerment theory are various microfinance and grassroots movements pioneered by people like Muhammad Yunus, who founded the Grameen Bank. Yunus believed that giving poor women seed finance as loans is crucial because it gives the individual the opportunity to grow their capital and, hopefully, move out of poverty. The bank was quite successful in this endeavour, providing seed capital to poor women and, in the process, lifting some of the beneficiaries from poverty (Alam, 2023). The economic empowerment theory can also be situated within the framework of feminist economics. Feminist economists, such as Nancy Folbre and Esther Boserup, argued that some of the challenges experienced by women are due to their position in the social hierarchy (Kreutzer et al., 2023). They argued that addressing gender disparities in the economic sphere through economic policies favouring women will address the challenges women face in a patriarchal society (Alex & Mathew, 2023).

In summary, the economic empowering theory is all about giving people resources that allow them to transcend poverty. These resources are not limited to capital but also knowledge to run enterprises successfully and engage markets. This means the economic empowerment theory is closely related to the human capability approach advanced by Amartya Sen and others.

The human capability approach (HCA) argues that people must be given the means to help them to be masters of their destinies. Sen (1985) developed the HCA to shift the focus of measuring human development outcomes from traditional economic indicators such as GDP towards human well-being indicators. The HCA is based on the idea that

people's well-being is enhanced when they can choose and pursue the lives they value and envision for themselves (Magoua & Li, 2023). The HCA has gained considerable attention in the field of development and social justice as a conceptual framework for evaluating the well-being of individuals and communities, the freedom required to achieve that well-being, and the values that underpin that freedom. In most cases, this freedom is associated with financial outcomes. Also, financially well-off individuals are better positioned to recover from disasters.

The discussion above illustrates the need for economic empowerment and the importance of promoting income-generating projects to build resilience. The work of WVI in Lesotho seeks to disrupt poverty by supporting SSABs, and it is hoped that this will result in more resilient individuals, households, and communities. Therefore, this study aims to determine the relationship between resilience and the economic empowerment initiatives spearheaded by WVI in Lesotho.

Specifically, this study sought to:

H₁: Determine if promoting individual resilience translates to improved overall resilience.

H₂: Determine if promoting household resilience translates to increased overall resilience.

H₃: Determine if promoting community resilience translates to increased overall resilience.

H₄: Determine the relationship between socio-economic empowerment and resilience.

To achieve these study objectives, the researcher leaned on two frameworks: the human capital theory and the economic empowerment theory. The human capital theory, popularised by economists such as Gary Becker, argues that imparting education and skills can enhance individuals' productivity and economic potential (Tan, 2014). It was reasoned that the people in the rural areas of Lesotho have a valuable asset in the form of land. Still, they experience challenges that prevent them from using the land optimally or for economic empowerment. These challenges include a lack of knowledge to improve production, a lack of capital, and poor market linkages. Socio-economic empowerment enables individuals or communities to control their economic resources and decision-making. This can include access to education, job opportunities, financial resources, and other tools that help individuals improve their economic status (World Bank, 2019). Through socio-economic empowerment, individuals can break free from cycles of poverty and achieve greater economic independence. This is particularly important in this study, which looks at resilience. It has been reported that socio-economic empowerment is often positively correlated with resilience to natural disasters such as storms and droughts (Cutter et al., 2012; Pricope et al., 2019).

Literature Review

The Role of Agriculture in Rural Economies

The idea that agriculture can be an effective tool for development is not universally shared. For example, Gollin et al. (2014) and Collier and Dercon (2014) have argued that rural poverty reduction must come from employment creation in the urban-industrial environment and a structural transformation of the economy. This view is congruent with the ideas the economist Sir Arthur Lewis presented in the 1950s. This award-winning economist, Sir Arthur Lewis, argued that with time, all countries would be able to grow their manufacturing industries to such that these industries would be able to absorb all excess labour. Without industrialization, this excess labour is often tied to the agricultural sector. Expanding a country's manufacturing base will, among other things, provide the population with higher-quality and high-paying jobs (Yuni et al., 2023). More importantly, wages in the agricultural sector would grow due to labour shortages, attracting more people to the industrial sector. The point where this happens is known as the Lewis Turning Point (LTP).

Interrogating the assumptions associated with the LTP reveals that, for a country to reach the LTP, it must grow its manufacturing industry. Unfortunately, most developing nations, including Lesotho, have not been able to grow their manufacturing capabilities over the past decades, and there are no indications of rapid industrialization in the coming decades (Yuni et al., 2023). This observation leaves agriculture as the most viable avenue for economically empowering people in countries like Lesotho through agriculture. The need to re-assess the role played by agriculture in economic development is further necessitated by the need to achieve the UN's SDG of ending extreme poverty by 2030. Faced with these realities, developmental organizations such as WVI continue to work towards improving rural agricultural output as one of the ways of economically empowering the people.

Though the definition of economic empowerment is not debated, save for minor differences in wording, there are challenges concerning how it is measured. This is mainly because many outcomes are observable in empowered individuals, and measuring any of these outcomes can suffice in most cases. For example, Doss et al. (2020) argued that economic empowerment is best measured by evaluating asset ownership, control, and use. This, to a greater extent, agrees with the assertions of Fox and Romero (2017), who, writing about women's economic empowerment, stated that determining the number of women in rural settings who own bank accounts is a reliable measure of empowerment. The rationale is that one can only have a bank account if they have the money to deposit; this means they will have a source of income and are masters of their financial matters.

This research focuses on three economic empowerment measures, comparing scores for individuals who were part of WVI Livelihood and Resilience Projects (LRPs) and those who were not. These measures are related to the socio-economic situation, factors preventing economic empowerment, and the socio-economic lives of project beneficiaries.

Small businesses, in general, are an essential driver of economic development as they expand the employment opportunities and incomes of the population (Murtazaev & Muhammadkhujja, 2022). In developing countries such as Lesotho, the lack of capital, technology, and knowledge limits entrepreneurial ventures that people can undertake in agriculture-related areas. Agriculture's relative accessibility likely explains why even the most developed or industrialized nations began with agriculture before expanding into more complex industries like manufacturing.

Promoting small-scale agribusinesses or entrepreneurship in Africa seems to be a sensible approach to fostering development. The idea of agro-based entrepreneurship has been heavily interrogated by scholars in recent years (Dias et al., 2019). Lans et al. (2013) note that entrepreneurship based on the agricultural sector is unique in that it often occurs in rural areas (Korsgaard et al., 2015). This presents a challenge since the rural folk are often already poor, so they cannot invest as much in their ventures and are less educated. Though these are challenges, this status quo presents an opportunity that has been exploited by relief and developmental agencies such as WVI. Relief agencies, such as World Vision International, have since sought to exploit the merits of agribusinesses to improve livelihoods by funding agribusiness ventures. In addition to requiring less capital, agro-based entrepreneurial ventures are popular because they utilize an abundant and often under-utilized resource in rural communities, such as land. This is an important insight as it magnifies the role of developmental agencies in helping change the economic fortunes of people experiencing poverty.

The Role of Entrepreneurship in Empowering Communities

Creating wealth through entrepreneurial ventures requires taking the major risks of deploying resources such as knowledge, time and equity. Unfortunately, people in rural areas do not always possess these resources, particularly knowledge and equity. The support of relief and development organizations such as USAID and WVI can partially alleviate this hindrance. These developmental organizations attempt to leverage the existing resources, particularly land, to improve livelihoods. Though the land is the platform on which entrepreneurial ventures in rural areas are based, it has been recognized that more benefits will accrue to the people if they also take part in the various value-addition processes associated with crops grown (Reardon et al., 2006). A large number of rural households in sub-Saharan Africa also engage in non-farm enterprises, and the contribution of these enterprises to employment and household incomes is increasing, not declining, as predicted by some economists. It is vital to support these enterprises as they are crucial in supporting the job creation for the millions of new job seekers entering Africa's labour market annually (Fox & Pimhidzai, 2013).

Entrepreneurship describes a dynamic process concerned with incremental wealth creation (Shailesh et al., 2013). Since entrepreneurship is concerned with wealth creation, it can be argued that it cannot be separated from the concept of economic empowerment. Economic empowerment is giving individuals, communities, or marginalized groups the tools, resources, and opportunities needed to achieve greater control over their economic circumstances. It entails giving individuals the capacity to participate in, contribute to and benefit from economic growth processes in ways that reward their contributions (Narayan-Parker, 2002). Mukorera (2020), for example, looked at the relationship

between entrepreneurship and economic empowerment in a study involving a group of South African women. The study revealed a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurship and economic empowerment. Though entrepreneurship only translates to economic empowerment and not necessarily political and social empowerment, it is a good start in empowering individuals in all aspects important in their lives (Mukorera, 2020). Failure to empower people economically leads to several adverse outcomes.

Though economic empowerment is often associated with an exodus from poverty, it is also crucial in promoting resilience (Duflo, 2012; Kabeer, 2005). The need for resilience in individuals, households, and communities has never been greater. This is because the environment in which humans exist in these contemporary times is much more variable. Most shocks that people experience can be, at least partly, addressed by deploying financial resources. Without sound economic empowerment initiatives, poverty is likely higher, and people are less likely to have the financial resources to deploy when needed. Working in Bangladesh, Maïtrot et al. (2021) found that poor people are often incapable of recovering sufficiently from the many natural disasters affecting the country. Comparing findings were reported in a United Nations report focusing on Zimbabwean women. In this report, it is stated that giving women economic opportunities was instrumental in increasing household resilience.

The Relationship Between Economic Empowerment and Resilience

Resilience building entails community transformation, particularly in poor rural communities. Interventions to transform communities can, therefore, help foster community resilience, and this transformation takes many different forms. It can be associated with building new infrastructure or increasing the economic fortunes of community members to acquire the capabilities needed to bounce from different forms of adversities. The latter is more relevant to this study. Economic empowerment initiatives transform individuals, and if the interventions are sustained and upscaled, they can lead to community transformation. The transformative power of economic activities, such as promoting SSABs, is therefore evident in outcomes such as increased resilience.

The critical function of economic activities in promoting resilience is illustrated in a study by Markantoni et al. (2023), who interrogated the role of private enterprises in building resilience in rural Scotland. Using secondary data, the researchers found that private enterprises employed many in rural Scotland, which allowed entire communities to be more resilient to economic shocks and natural disasters. Though not solely derived from agriculture, the incomes generated by inhabitants of respective areas supported many cottage industries. In addition to increased incomes for the rural people, it was also found that rural businesses increase the diversification of the local economy and, in doing so, promote broader rural community resilience. This phenomenon, as one can imagine, can also occur in Rural Lesotho, given the challenge of employment faced by the people.

Another study conducted in Fiji focusing on the role of women in building community resilience also identified women's economic empowerment as one of the critical steps in achieving more significant rates of resilience (Singh et al., 2022). Though this study focused on women, some parallels can be deduced between the communities studied and those in rural Lesotho. Both communities rely on food sources that are vulnerable to the

vagaries of the climate, and, in that sense, they lack resilience. The researchers indicated that the communities in Fiji relied a lot on natural resources provided by the forest, and in Rural Lesotho, people rely on rain-fed agriculture. It can be argued that in both cases, an unfavourable climate translates to challenges such as food insecurities. Also, it is not easy to monetize forestry resources, and it is also challenging to monetize rain-fed crops since, in rural areas, yields are hardly enough to feed households until the next harvest (Dick-Sagoe et al., 2023). It is, therefore, not surprising that the researchers identified that increasing income-generating opportunities for community members translates to increased resilience. This study helps to illustrate the relationship between resilience and economic empowerment.

Methodology

Sampling

Data was collected from 283 households purposefully selected in districts where WVI is implementing its Livelihoods and Resilience Projects (LRPs). The participants are individuals who were part of at least a single SSAB. Individual households were selected through random sampling within the project communities.

Research instrument

The data was collected using a 7-point Likert scale-based instrument ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). A Likert scale with many levels was preferred because it allowed the researcher to collect more detailed information from the participants (Robinson, 2024). The questions contained in the instrument were created by the researcher using insights gathered from literature relevant to the study. The first section of the questionnaire focused on gathering demographic information from the respondents, including variables such as gender, age, education, and experience. Section 2 examined resilience indicators of individuals, households, and communities. Section 3 evaluated the socio-economic condition of the project beneficiaries: economic empowerment. The survey instrument facilitated the collection of responses from participants who had engaged in the project via the SSAB groups, enabling them to respond based on their experiential knowledge. After the surveys were designed, a statistician reviewed them and made recommendations.

Pilot study

A pilot study was conducted among 30 enumerators recruited from the study area who had undergone training on the research tools. Brink et al. (2012) define a pilot study as a reduced-scale iteration of a more extensive investigation. The pilot study was conducted to assess the efficacy of the questionnaire and identify any challenges that respondents may face when completing it. The objective of the pilot study is to conduct a preliminary assessment of the questionnaire to gather the essential data required for enhancing the viability of the study. The questionnaire was also piloted to assess the face validity and clarity of the questions. The piloting was done with a small convenience sample of participants. In the pilot study, it was observed that specific words and phrases posed challenges in terms of comprehension for a subset of the participants. Modifications were

made to the questionnaire in response to the observations and feedback gathered during the pre-test phase. Another factor considered during the pre-test phase was assessing the instrument's internal consistency for collecting quantitative data.

Data collection

World Vision Lesotho distributed a formal letter through its Area Development Programme offices in the respective programme districts to facilitate data collection within the communities. The purpose of the letter was to introduce the researcher to the Community Councillors. The researcher additionally distributed an introductory letter to the community leaders via the World Vision Area Development Programme, elucidating the study's objectives and the methodology employed in the research. The introduction facilitated the researcher and enumerators to establish convenient entry into the communities and engage with the project participants for the data collection. The respondents who participated in the study were located and identified at their respective homes.

The quantitative data collection was facilitated using the KoboCollect tool on a smartphone from April 24 to May 14, 2023. Using a mobile device in the data collection facilitated the efficient acquisition, preservation, and administration of the research data. One of the benefits associated with utilizing mobile phones for data collection is the facilitation of paperless research. This approach allows for capturing data in various intricate formats, including quantitative data, descriptive data, photographs, and coordinates. Participation in the survey was voluntary, and no incentive was offered to the participants.

Data analysis

The data obtained from the questionnaire were analyzed using inferential statistics. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 28 and SmartPLS 4 were used for the data analysis. The results were organized and presented using tables and graphs to ensure a better understanding of the data analyzed. Following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) recommendations, a two-step approach for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) has been used for data analysis.

A Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted to develop the measurement model in the first step. The CFA was performed on the measurement variables to examine the model's overall fit, reliability and validity. The first step in generating PLS-SEM findings involves the assessment of the measurement model, which pertains to examining the validity and reliability of the measures (Alshirah et al., 2021). The measurement model was assessed through construct convergence, factor loadings, values of Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability and average variance extracted (AVE), with the following criteria: 0.7, 0.5 and 0.7, respectively, following Hair et al. (2019). The convergent validity of the model was assessed using the factor loadings and their statistical tests, and the average variance was extracted. The Fornell-Larcker criterion (Fornell and Larcker, 1981) and Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) were used to test the discriminant validity of the measurement model.

The proposed structural model was tested using PLS-SEM to examine the causal relationships among all constructs. The hypotheses were tested using partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The PLS-SEM is a multivariate statistical technique that allows for the simultaneous estimation of several relationships between exogenous and endogenous constructs in a single model. The PLS-SEM with SmartPLS 4.0 statistical software was used to analyze the research model and test the hypotheses. The PLS-SEM was chosen as the estimation method due to the predictive nature of the study.

PLS-SEM is preferred to SEM because it provides optimal predictive power (Fornell and Bookstein, 1982; Lin et al., 2020). In addition, PLS-SEM modelling is particularly useful for testing exploratory models formed by numerous variables under normality and non-normality data distribution assumptions (Hair et al., 2016). PLS-SEM is particularly effective in exploratory studies focused on prediction, which includes determining drivers of endogenous constructs (Hair Jr et al., 2011; Hair Jr et al., 2014). Exploratory research is fundamental when theory is less developed (Hair Jr et al., 2016). Based on the above, PLS-SEM was used to test the hypotheses and analyze the gathered data. We also examined the standardized direct, indirect and total effects. A direct effect represents a link between two constructs, whilst an indirect effect represents the effect of a construct on another construct through an intervening construct. A construct's total effect on an outcome construct is the sum of the direct and indirect effects.

Findings

The study sought to determine the relationship between being part of at least one WVI LRP and selected empowerment measures. Data was collected from 277 randomly chosen participants. The demographic characteristics of the study population are summarised in Table 1.

Data for this study was collected from 277 participants, 198 (70.04 %) of whom were male. Most of the participants (181) were over 50 years of age. There were only four participants who were below the age of 30 years. Concerning education, most of the participants (164) only had primary school education.

The study participants' demographic characteristics help explain why the rural communities have not developed at the same pace as observed in the developed world. The low education attainment, for instance, betrays the need for outside agencies to come in and help with economic empowerment initiatives. The lack of education means that people are less likely to adopt newer farming methods resilient to climate shocks (Li et al., 2024).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Study Sample

Household Head Demographic Traits		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	194	0.70
	Female	83	0.30
Total		277	100
Age Category	<30	4	1.40
	31-40	43	15.5
	41-50	49	17.70
	50+	181	65.30
Total		283	100
Level of Education	None	34	12.30
	Primary	164	59.20
	Secondary	49	17.31
	High School	27	9.54
	Certificate	1	0.40
	Diploma	1	0.40
	Other	1	0.40
Total		277	100
Marital status	Single	17	6.10
	Married	178	64.31
	Divorced/Separated	17	6.10
	Widowed	64	22.61
Total		277	100

Table 2 displays the factor loadings, Cronbach alpha, composite reliability and average variance extracted for the measurement model. All the indicators were significantly loaded onto their respective constructs, with factor loadings ranging from 0.815 to 0.922. All the factor loading was more than 0.80, which is strong evidence of unidimensionality and convergent validity. Results indicate that the measures have good levels of reliability and convergent validity. The Cronbach alpha values are greater than 0.700 and range from 0.732 to 0.896.

The AVE values extracted range from 0.744 to 0.828, suggesting that each construct was related to their respective indicators. The AVE values are greater than 0.5, indicating that the constructs explained more than half of the variability observed in the variables. The composite reliability of all the latent constructs in the measurement model was more than 0.70. This indicates that the latent constructs are reliable and consistent. Results indicated that these measures showed good levels of reliability and convergent validity.

Table 2. Measurement of validity and reliability assessment

Construct	Loading	Cronbach alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Individual resilience				
Q9: I am able to generate income from my farming, employment, and other skilled-based occupation.	0.886	0.779	0.900	0.818
Q10: I am able to make plans for my farming business and other income-generating activities and accomplish them	0.922			
Household resilience				
Q31: My family run out of food for More than a day	0.882	0.835	0.897	0.744
Q32: There were occasions when my family cut the size of meals or skipped a meal because there was food or no money to buy food	0.889			
Q33: There were occasions when children in my household did not have enough food to eat (ate less than 3 food groups and less than 3 times a day)	0.815			
Community resilience				
Q54: Disaster management training was conducted for my community last year	0.874	0.896	0.935	0.828
Q55: My community is currently taking steps toward disaster/ hazard preparedness	0.933			
Q56: The level of my community's preparedness in relation to disaster management is good	0.921			
Resilience				
Q36: Community disaster committees have capacity to mitigate and respond to disasters	0.867	0.732	0.881	0.788
Q53: My community has a disaster preparedness plan	0.907			
Socio-economic empowerment				
Q66: My standard of living has improved as a result of my income-generating activities (IGA)	0.883	0.882	0.927	0.809
Q67: My business or IGAs are growing well	0.919			
Q69: I can sustain my improved living condition through my IGAs	0.896			

The HTMT values regarded as the current ideal criterion for evaluating discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2019; Henseler et al., 2015) are reported in Table 3. Each of the provided HTMT results falls below the threshold value of 0.85. This is a prerequisite for discriminant validity since it proves that each variable is distinct from every other (Hair et al., 2019; Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 3. Discriminant validity by HTMT criterion

Constructs	1	2	3	4	5
Community resilience					
Household resilience	0.041				
Individual resilience	0.220	0.277			
Resilience	0.777	0.091	0.194		
Socio-economic empowerment	0.134	0.231	0.669	0.20	

The square root of AVE (shown on the diagonal) and the inter-construct correlation are presented in Table 4. Following the recommendations of Fornell and Larcker (1981), conditions for indicating that discriminant validity is present were satisfied in the measurement model since the square root of all AVE values are much higher than the inter-construct correlation coefficient of target constructs. This suggests that the measurement model exhibits good discriminant validity.

Finally, model fit measures using PLS-SEM were tested. The standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) of the research model was 0.068, which is lower than 0.08, indicating good model fit (Hu and Bentler, 1998). The normed fit index (NFI) was 0.800, slightly below the recommended 0.90 threshold (Hu and Bentler, 1998).

Table 4. Discriminant validity by Fornell-Larcker criterion

Constructs	1	2	3	4	5
Community resilience	0.910				
Household resilience	0.032	0.862			
Individual resilience	0.185	0.228	0.904		
Resilience	0.796	0.022	0.140	0.887	
Socio-economic empowerment	0.119	0.211	0.559	0.158	0.899

Assessment of structural model

The research hypotheses were tested and validated with PLS-SEM using SmartPLS 4 software. The bootstrapping method was carried out with 5000 re-samples following Hair et al. (2019). To assess the impact of socio-economic empowerment on resilience, the standardized direct and indirect and total effects were examined.

From Table 5, community resilience mediates the relationship between socio-economic empowerment and resilience ($\beta = 0.095$, p -value=0.050, CI=0.00 to 0.19). However, household resilience ($\beta = -0.034$, p -value=0.212, CI= -0.088 to 0.019) and individual resilience ($\beta = -0.002$, p -value=0.78, CI= -0.02 to 0.01) do not mediate the relationship between socio-economic empowerment and resilience.

Table 5. Structural Indirect paths showing hypotheses test results

Path	Coefficient	t-statistics	CI		p-value
			Lower limit (2.5%)	Upper limit (97.5%)	
Socio-economic empowerment -> Individual resilience -> Resilience	-0.034	1.248	-0.088	0.019	0.212
Socio-economic empowerment -> Household resilience -> Resilience	-0.002	0.279	-0.02	0.014	0.78
Socio-economic empowerment -> Community resilience -> Resilience	0.095	1.964	0.00	0.19	0.05

Table 6. Structural paths showing hypotheses test results (Total indirect effect)

Path	Coefficient	t-statistics	Lower CI (2.5%)	Upper CI (97.5%)	p-value
Socio-economic empowerment -> Resilience	0.059	1.081	-0.048	0.166	0.28

The total indirect effect of socio-economic empowerment on resilience is positive but not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.059$, p-value=0.28, CI= -0.048 to 0.166).

Table 7. Structural paths showing hypotheses test results (Total effects)

Path	Coefficient	t-statistics	CI		p-value
			Lower limit (2.5%)	Upper limit (97.5%)	
Community resilience -> Resilience	0.796	24.291	0.729	0.858	0.000
Household resilience -> Resilience	-0.011	0.29	-0.089	0.065	0.772
Individual resilience -> Resilience	-0.060	1.262	-0.153	0.034	0.207
Socio-economic empowerment -> Community resilience	0.119	1.97	0.000	0.24	0.049
Socio-economic empowerment -> Household resilience	0.211	3.691	0.108	0.326	0.000
Socio-economic empowerment -> Individual resilience	0.559	12.897	0.473	0.643	0.000
Socio-economic empowerment -> Resilience	0.158	2.687	0.043	0.271	0.007

The findings showed that community resilience had a positive and statistically significant impact on resilience ($\beta = 0.796$, p-value=0.000). Household resilience had a

negative and statistically non-significant impact on resilience ($\beta = -0.011$, p -value=0.772). Individual resilience had a negative and statistically non-significant impact on resilience ($\beta = -0.060$, p -value=0.207).

The relationship between socio-economic empowerment and community resilience was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.119$, p -value=0.049). Socio-economic empowerment had a positive and statistically significant impact on household resilience ($\beta = 0.211$, p -value=0.000), individual resilience ($\beta = 0.559$, p -value=0.000) and resilience ($\beta = 0.099$, p -value=0.044), individual resilience ($\beta = 0.559$, p -value=0.000) and resilience ($\beta = 0.158$, p -value=0.007).

Figure 1. Structural model for direct and mediated paths

The PLS-SEM model was used to examine the hypotheses based on the proposed framework in Figure 1. The results of the PLS-SEM structural model, including the path coefficients and path significance, are presented in Figure 2. Not all the path coefficients demonstrated significance. Some of the results were in contrast to the hypothesis. From the results of the PLS-SEM, 2 out of the 6 proposed hypotheses were supported.

Importance-Performance Map Analysis (IPMA)

The results of PLS-SEM do not provide information on how resilience is affected by increasing one point of individual, household, community and socio-economic empowerment indicators and which constructs should be prioritized. To further understand the predictors of the model, the IPMA was employed in PLS-SEM.

The importance-performance map analysis extends the standard PLS-SEM analysis findings by including the importance and performance of each construct. Table 1 and Figure 1 presents the results of the IPMA. A scatter plot of the information in Table 2 produces the importance-performance map, as shown in Figure 1. The x-axis represents the importance of household resilience, individual resilience, community resilience, and socio-economic empowerment in explaining resilience, while the y-axis depicts the performance of the constructs in terms of their average rescaled latent variable scores.

The results in Figure 2 and Table 8 indicate that community resilience was most important in determining resilience. The next important construct is socio-economic empowerment. The IPMA results revealed that community resilience, with an importance index of 0.796, and socio-economic empowerment, with an importance index of 0.158, are the two significant predictors of resilience.

On the other hand, household resilience performed considerably higher than the rest of the constructs. Household resilience, socio-economic empowerment and individual resilience exhibited performance indices of 57.666, 48.648 and 47.781, respectively. Thus, household resilience, socio-economic empowerment and individual resilience are the key drivers of resilience.

Table 8. Importance-Performance Map Analysis (IPMA) results

Predictors	Performance Index	Importance Index
Community resilience	26.572	0.796
Household resilience	57.666	-0.011
Individual resilience	47.781	-0.060
Socio-economic empowerment	48.648	0.158

Figure 2. IPMA results

Discussion and Implications

The Relationship Between Individual Resilience and Overall Resilience.

The first hypothesis tested the relationship between individual resilience and overall resilience. The analysis from this study did not find significant relationships between individual and overall resilience. Individual resilience had a negative and statistically non-significant impact on resilience ($\beta = -0.060$, $p\text{-value} = 0.207$). This is incongruent with several studies that have consistently shown that individual resilience often leads to overall resilience (Ali et al., 2023). This unexpected result was also replicated when the impacts of household resilience on overall resilience were analyzed.

The Relationship Between Household Resilience and Overall Resilience.

The second hypothesis tested the relationship between household resilience and overall resilience. According to this study's findings, household resilience had a negative and statistically non-significant impact on resilience ($\beta = -0.011$, $p\text{-value} = 0.772$). This finding contradicts findings by other researchers who found a significant relationship between household resilience and overall resilience (Phuong et al., 2023). One possible explanation why household and individual resilience did not significantly impact overall resilience is due to the multi-faceted nature of resilience on a global scale (Giske & Pinheiro, 2023). The multi-faceted nature of resilience on a global scale means that some aspects of resilience are beyond the control of a household or an individual. In this study, some of the questions focusing on overall resilience sought to understand the role different individuals play in the decision-making processes within their communities. Due to the nature of governance in some parts of Africa, particularly in rural areas, ordinary people are not always asked about their opinions on matters that affect them (Gohori & van der Merwe, 2024; Magoola et al., 2023). Wang et al. (2023), for example, argued that promoting resilience in communities requires all community members to have a say in issues that affect their communities. It can, therefore, be argued that in the absence of legitimate community engagement initiatives, overall resilience is likely to be low. In most parts of Africa, elected officials often have a monopoly when it comes to decision making (Aiyede, 2023). This finding can, therefore, be taken as a call for community leaders to democratize decision-making processes.

The Relationship Between Community Resilience and Overall Resilience.

The third hypothesis tested the relationship between community resilience and overall resilience. The findings from this study showed that community resilience had a positive and statistically significant impact on resilience ($\beta = 0.796$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). The finding supports the abovementioned explanation that there is a need to involve the entire community in decision-making processes. Resilient communities have strong social networks and relationships, which enhance the ability of individuals and groups to cope with and recover from disasters. Strong social ties enable the sharing of resources, information, and emotional support, which are crucial during and after crises (Zhang & Sung, 2023). This means the positive impacts of community collaboration on resilience may be difficult to isolate or tease out if analyses are limited to individual or household levels.

The Relationship Between Socio-economically Empowerment Initiatives and Resilience.

The fourth hypothesis tested the direct relationship between economic empowerment and resilience and various scales, from individual to overall resilience. It was observed that economic empowerment initiatives significantly impacted resilience at all levels, individual, household, community, and overall resilience. This is an important finding because it shows, for the first time, that WVI's economic empowerment initiatives positively affect the levels of resilience in the studied communities.

According to the economic empowerment theory, economic empowerment initiatives can improve people's resilience by giving them the resources they need to mitigate the challenges they face due to several forms of adversity they may encounter. These resources are usually in the form of financial capabilities accompanying economically successful enterprises. In the context of this study, the enterprises were all based on various forms of agribusinesses. World Vision International provided the project beneficiaries with capital and knowledge to ensure that the various SSABs were economically viable, which resulted in more disposable income for the beneficiaries. The positive impacts of economic empowerment initiatives on resilience have been reported elsewhere. A study conducted by Liu et al. (2023) in rural China found that supporting women to take full advantage of the vegetable value chain resulted in greater resilience in terms of food security and financial shocks. In this study, it was observed that vegetable growers have a limited earning window due to the perishability of vegetables. The women were empowered with simple technologies to preserve and sell their farm produce for much longer. This economic empowerment initiative is comparable to what is promoted by WVI in Lesotho. Increasing farm output, penetration of new markets, and extending the growing season through irrigation increased farmer incomes, leading to the ability to fund activities to address challenges brought by personal disasters or climate shocks.

According to the findings of this study, the relationship between socio-economic empowerment and community resilience was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.119$, p -value=0.049). The positive relationship between community resilience and economic empowerment can be explained in several ways. Literature suggests that economically empowering communities result in more money circulating within the community. This will result in the emergence of many other businesses, a phenomenon that will increase resilience by diversifying sources of income (He et al., 2022). The presence of different businesses also means that the community members will have more services they require closer to them and may not need to go to large cities to procure necessities. One can think of the availability of building materials, a resource that will be in demand during a natural disaster such as heavy rains. People in a community with building material retailers will be able to repair their dwellings much faster, which means they will be more resilient than in a situation where they would have had to travel to bigger towns to procure the material. Bulturbayevich (2022), for example, reported that small businesses in small towns make the procurement of necessities cheaper for the town inhabitants, making their meagre incomes go further. Also, an economically vibrant community will attract different forms of entrepreneurs, such as artisans and builders. The presence of such professionals will significantly improve the community's overall resilience as they will not have to wait for outside help in the event of a disaster.

Finally, the analysis revealed that socio-economic empowerment significantly positively affects overall resilience, indicating a cumulative impact across multiple levels ($\beta = 0.158$, p -value = 0.007). This finding suggests that initiatives to enhance socio-economic conditions through improved food security and diversified livelihoods can effectively bolster individuals, households, and communities' ability to withstand and recover from various shocks and stresses. The positive effect size ($\beta = 0.158$) and statistically significant p -value ($p = 0.007$) underscore the robustness of this relationship, implying that even modest improvements in socio-economic empowerment can lead to meaningful enhancements in resilience. Therefore, policymakers and development

practitioners should prioritize and scale up such interventions to foster sustainable and resilient communities.

Before this study, there was no published information on the impacts of the SSAB approach by WVI in rural Lesotho. It can be argued that this approach has positively impacted livelihoods, particularly economic empowerment. Promoting economic empowerment is essential because, among other outcomes, it translates to increased resilience.

The positive outcomes of the SSAB approach can be explained from the lens of the HCA. As discussed earlier, the HCA is concerned with giving people the capabilities to determine their future. The human capability approach stresses the importance of agency (Leßmann, 2022). That is the ability of individuals to act and make decisions that affect their lives. In the context of this study, WVI intervened in the communities by deploying resources the various farmer groups needed. The farmers did the rest of the work and chose how they utilized any proceeds from their enterprises.

Future Studies

Further research could be conducted to assess the sustained impact of agricultural interventions and economic empowerment initiatives in Lesotho. One way to do this is through a longitudinal study that evaluates the effectiveness of programs like World Vision International's Livelihoods and Resilience Programme (LRP) on participants' socio-economic outcomes over time. A comparative analysis of different types of interventions implemented by various Lesotho organizations could also be pursued. Additionally, exploring gender dynamics within these interventions would provide valuable insights into how male and female participants experience and benefit from such programs differently, leading to more gender-equitable strategies. Qualitative studies could explore the barriers and enablers of economic empowerment in rural settings. Investigations into climate resilience practices and technology adoption could also shed light on enhancing sustainability and productivity. Furthermore, understanding community-level impacts, policy implications, and innovations in agricultural practices would inform more targeted interventions and policies for sustainable poverty reduction and inclusive economic development in Lesotho.

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